

NEWSPAPERS AS AN ENGLISH TEACHING TOOL

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Annotation. This article is devoted to analyzing the importance of using newspapers as an English teaching tool and finding the ways how to use newspapers in teaching process.

Key words: mass media, newspapers, periodicals, language teaching, language skills, tools, press, articles.

Since mass media have become one of an indispensable part of modern society, this developing trend may serve as a great means in English teaching process. Media “inform, amuse, startle, anger, entertain, thrill, but very seldom leave anyone untouched”[1]. Newspapers are considered to be one of the most powerful sources of sharing information and enriching knowledge bank. Therefore, the use of newspaper materials in teaching the language can serve as a motivating element that contributes to the development of cognitive activity of students and the desire for self-improvement in their mastery of the language in the learning process.

Most newspapers are linguistically up-to-date and provide valuable linguistic data. Having a wide diversity of text types and language styles and being an invaluable source of authentic material, English-language newspapers provide a natural source of the varieties of written English. The original material has ample opportunities for teaching different types of speech activity: reading, speaking, writing. Moreover, newspapers may be used for the cultural information they transmit. The more widely students read, the greater their understanding of this cultural meaning will be.

Reading newspapers has a beneficial effect on the emotional background of students. The process of reading newspapers gives pleasure, as it reflects a real, “living language”. However, it is necessary to select material according to the age categories and different levels of language proficiency. Typically, newspaper articles are structured in such a way that a familiar type of a text can be seen.

Newspapers cover everyday events, everyday topics. It presents a huge variety of genres and compositions.

Nowadays, with rapid technological changes in mass communications and Internet development, it has become possible to access thousands of newspapers worldwide. The Internet has increasingly become a major source of online versions of newspapers for language teachers and learners. All that is needed is to find the web sites and click on them. For example, English-language newspapers such as The Guardian, The Washington Post, The Times, The New York Times, and The Uzdaily are recommendable as teaching and learning materials for teachers and students of English. All these newspapers can easily be found in the Internet, and their electronic versions are described below [5-9].

One of the useful periodicals for teaching and learning English may be the English-language newspaper "The Times (of London)" published by the British, which provides information on domestic and foreign policy and economy of the country, national events, and also gives a qualitative overview of incidents in the world. This edition is also interesting because the presentation in it is often conducted using the famous subtle English humor, which brings a fair amount of uniqueness to the reading of articles. There is also "Times2" section devoted to social subjects, where materials about life style features, columns of sport, music, fashion, books, and TV programs are published. The "Past six days" section allows the users to read the events of the previous week. Besides, the electronic version of the newspaper has "Times radio", where diverse subjects (from serious to entertaining ones) are discussed.

Another most popular and accessible British newspaper is "The Guardian", also published in English by the British. It is suitable for students with different levels of English proficiency and well-established language skills. The articles are devoted to issues of domestic and foreign policy, psychology, economics, and so forth. In terms of language turnover, it is necessary to note that most English sentences are extended, that is, students will have the opportunity to focus on full-length structures. Unlike other British newspapers, theguardian.com, the online version of this newspaper, does not have a paid subscription on the network and the content on the site is available to absolutely all users for free. The main page of the publication primarily redirects to the British version of the publication. The reader can also select the US and Australian versions. The first page consists of a collection of the latest and most popular news and articles from all sections and headings, graphically highlighted, and having a title, a short description, as well as a mention of the number of comments, links to related articles. In the electronic version of this newspaper users can find and watch recordings with speeches of

various political figures. Also, some news, especially in the Top News category, is accompanied by illustrations. Interestingly, on the official website of The Guardian (theguardian.co.uk) there is a free archive of all issues of the newspaper for all the years that have passed, which exactly repeat its printed versions.

“The Washington Post”, published by Americans, is a newspaper for fashion, travel and politics lovers. This edition is suitable just for those who are just starting their acquaintance with the English-language press, since this is where simple grammatical constructions are used, so the sentences are easy to read. There is also a Lifestyle section where readers can find publications on the topic of fashion, travel, recipes, home and garden, and even kidspost (a special section for children, where a great variety of interesting articles are presented). When visiting The Washington Post’s online site, one can notice that any article will be very long. These voluminous posts are with a lot of text and visual information. They are always thrice the length of regular Uzbek publications. In one article from The Washington Post, readers can find all the information they need, from digital data to quotes, comments and author jokes. After reading such a voluminous article, readers have no desire to switch to other sources in search of missing facts. In almost any post in The Washington Post, there will be links not only to several official sources, but also to the comments of authoritative experts and analysts. In addition, users can find links to twitter of the heroes of the publication, comments on Facebook and other sources where there is at least some information about the event. In addition to the usual newspaper articles, the electronic version of this newspaper also has video news, which is published in the PostTV section. Such devices can provide opportunities for practicing and improving listening skills when users access these video news.

“The New York Times” is an American analogue of the British newspaper. It covers financial, economic, political events. The newspaper has a reputation as a respectable one that avoids sensationalism and is responsible for the reliability of the materials published on its pages. The editors strive to publish information on all major events taking place in the country and abroad, and to comment on them impartially. This edition presents a typical American English. The language, especially in large articles or an opinion section, is relatively complex, but articles on general topics are quite comprehensible. This newspaper consists of several sections such as World, U.S, Politics, New York, Business, Opinion, Tech, Sports, Science, Health, Arts, Style, Books, Food, Travel, Magazine, T Magazine, Real Estate, Video, and so on. In addition to basic text news, charts or graphs are often found on the right. Headings are updated as information becomes available. Unlike printed standards, the submission of material in the Internet edition is

distinguished by creativity: the use of images, photographs, diagrams, tables, statements of the subjective opinion of the journalist and the use of colloquial vocabulary are allowed. And the Video section of the online version of The New York Times is very popular with site visitors. It includes the following sections: U. S. & Politics, International, N. Y., Op-Docs, Opinion, Times Documentaries, Business, Tech, Culture, Style, T Magazine, Health, Food, Travel, Sports, Real Estate, Science. It is more convenient for Internet users to observe a dynamic and combined visual series of information than text combined with illustrations.

Teachers and students of English may also find useful English-language newspapers in Uzbekistan. A newspaper “UzDaily”, an online media, covers not only economy, finance, technologies, culture, tourism and sport of the country, but worldwide events as well. Most articles are restrained and informative and aim to spread positive image of Uzbekistan. This electronic newspaper offers its users the opportunity to choose the language (Uzbek, Russian, or English), which can be considered as an advantage of this periodical: when reading an article in English and facing some complicated sentences, readers can change the language to understand the meaning of some structures.

Another important issue about newspaper use is collection of materials. It is an on-going process and worth doing it. Choosing and collecting short articles, weather forecasts, advertisements, headlines is a hard task, but they can be used at a later time or more than once for different students. So, it is necessary to be careful in collecting newspaper materials when teaching the language. It is good to categorize the material under certain titles, headlines, advertisements, etc. or under topic titles, sport, cinema, relationship, according to language level of students, etc. Of great importance is the use of photographs and illustrations. Before reading an article, students may be given some questions to predict the content of the material. The questions can be posed as follows:

Who do you think the person is in the picture?

What will happen next?

Where do you think it is happening?

Why is the person happy/angry/sad?

Who is the person mentioned in the heading?

What part of paper do you think the headline appears in? Sport? News?

Then, after checking the students' answers, reading becomes more meaningful, because now it is not just browsing through the text, but looking for specific information. It is also possible to write out key sentences of the article, as this technique develops reading in order to understand the main idea. Looking for synonyms and synonymous expressions such as “prices go through the roof” and

“prices increase dramatically” is a good thing to do while reading a newspaper article in English. This will help students not just look at new words, but learn them in context. It is also possible to give synonymous phrases while reading an article. For instance, when reading an article on the struggle of peoples against colonial oppression and racism, the following expressions can be used: to eliminate racism, to abolish inequality, the colonial people are to liquidate apartheid, to put an end to colonial oppression. It will be beneficial for students to use different options of one phrase.

The involvement of students in pre-activity, while-activity preparation techniques, in the selection of materials and in carefully designing the tasks are the key to success. Here are some pre-activity and while-activity preparation techniques that can be used in combination with one another[3]:

- Give the students the materials before the lesson, ask them to look for vocabulary at home
- Explain any key vocabulary in the materials
- Summarize the newspaper item
- Ask the students to brainstorm what they know about the newspaper item
- Tell the students the headline and show any accompanying photograph
- Before reading, write on the board and explain key vocabulary
- Ask the students to predict the story-line
- Allow your students to use a dictionary during the activity
- Encourage your students to go for the overall meaning of a text, rather than to understand every word
- Encourage your students to bring to their reading their own world knowledge
- Try to help the students in understanding the grammatical complexity of the text, facilitate to assimilate the density of information, guess the low-frequency vocabulary, etc.

The newspaper activities might be about the headlines, headline combinations, articles, categorizing articles, exchanging the news, filling in the gaps, news in brief, photographs, predicting photographs, famous faces, photo captions, putting the picture in the story, advertisements, classifying adds, job interviews, horoscopes, weather forecast, special interest groups, newspaper puzzles, crosswords, and many others[4].

To sum up, using English newspapers in teaching and learning English is very important because it develops students' creative powers, enriches the vocabulary of students, increases their language level, contributes to understanding the way of thinking of people speaking English.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Biagi Sh. Media Reader - New York: Wadsworth Publishing Company, 1996
2. Mol' A. Language and the Media. In Annual review of Applied Linguistics - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008
3. Sanderson P. Using Newspapers in the Classroom - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2002
4. Vilma T. Teaching English Through Mass Media, journal «Acta Didactica Napocensia»,2009
5. <https://www.theguardian.com/uk/commentisfree>
6. https://www.washingtonpost.com/?reload=true&_=1612462333729
7. <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/>
8. <https://www.nytimes.com/>
9. <https://uzdaily.uz/en>
10. Rahmonova, M. (2021). Patriotic ideas in the works by fitrat: theoretical and practical harmony. ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL, 11(2), 1466-1474..
11. Raxmonova, M. (2022). ZAMONAVIY TADBIRKOR AYOL PSIXOLOGIYASINING KASBGA YO'NALGANLIGI. Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture, 2(6), 204-206.
12. Xasanovna, R. M. (2022). ZAMONAVIY TADBIRKOR AYOL PSIXOLOGIYASINING MUHIM KOMPONENTLARI. BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 394-396..
13. Xasanovna, R. M. (2022). ZAMONAVIY TADBIRKOR AYOLLARNING IJTIMOYIY FAOLLIGI. Science and innovation, 1(B3), 497-500.
14. Khasanovna, R. M. (2022). The uniqueness of personality traits in modern entrepreneurial women. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 12(6), 304-307.
15. Khasanovna, M. R. (2022). The entrepreneur's psychology of family relations.